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CONSUMER BEHAVIOUR OF WOMEN FOR DURABLE PRODUCTS IN KERALA

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ABSTRACT

“Many things that were considered as luxuries till about ten years ago have become necessities for more people today”. And in case of durable Products consumption it has happened also as which were luxury at once becomes necessity now. Consumer centric marketing style is predominant in durables which in turn revolve round the consumer purchase attitude. Today women’s are chief purchase officer controlling 85% of all purchase decision .In India women hold more than 25% of the white collar jobs in sector like IT, ITES, Pharmaceutical, Biotechnology, market research, financial services ,advertising, marketing and media. The new Indian woman is a hard working professional woman. The research paper deals with the study of women purchase attitude with special reference to consumer durables in Kerala.

Keywords: Women consumers, behaviour, consumption, durable products, purchase attitude, necessity.

Introduction

Kerala is a highly developed market for consumer products and all leading national marketers have been trying to ensure a fare share of the market. However, this market is quite unique in several respects compared to other states. Some of the prevailing assumptions are that conspicuous consumption is relatively high in Kerala, purchasing power of the average household is comparatively more, rural urban differences are less pronounced and the whole state is an extended urban market. Whatever might be the unique characteristics of the Kerala market, the uniqueness necessarily stems from the culture and social structure in the state. For evolving marketing strategies, it is imperative that marketers have a proper understanding of the behaviour of consumers in Kerala.

Women today are upwardly mobile and expect to gain life satisfaction from the job rewards of money, power, leadership, prestige and esteem. The spread of education, increased cost of living, changed norms of measuring one's status in terms of income, and the change in men's attitude induce more and more women to come out and accept jobs outside their homes. An important feature of the dual earner family is the segregation of work and family life. Traditionally women are expected to work at home and this is considered most essential for the subsistence of the family. With a large number of women taking up jobs, necessitated by economic and psychological factors, the role of women as home maker cum wage earner is being widely accepted in Kerala. This has necessitated structural changes in the family organization. In the Kerala culture, male partner is considered the real head of the family who takes different decisions pertaining to the functioning of the family. Women were traditionally considered inferior to men especially in the matter of decision making. The male dominance in this regard was due to the higher status and social position that men enjoyed in terms of their higher educational levels, income and social skills and cultural. Women in Kerala take up job primarily to meet the economic necessities of their homes and not for the psychological needs of power, esteem, authority and greater freedom or greater female autonomy.

Women Consumer:

In earlier times, women possessed no right in any field. Only men made decisions. Women were treated as having no right, but them only puppets in the hands of men. But now the stage has changed. Along

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with men, women are also stepping out on equal footing. About more than 75% of purchases of a family is being made by women. Their position and status have come up, and are still coming up.

Women consumers are while shopping. They wander from shop to shop. They are keen in style, colour, beauty and economy in purchasing. They look and compare the products with other products. They always compare the quality and the price of similar products. They take time in inspecting the products and in making a decision whether to buy or not. They are conservative. They expect more products for less money. They may go even for comparison, after the purchase is made. They try to find difference in products purchased comparing them with the products purchased by a neighboring woman. They want a superior position everywhere, even in purchase too. They may be given a warm welcome on their arrival. They may be asked with a smile, as to what their requirements are.

Consumer Behaviour of Women:

The profile and role of the woman has been undergoing significant changes. Today, she is educated and in many cases employed. The percentage of working woman has actually been growing steady pace. Their purchasing power has increased: thus the demand for product categories like cosmetics, package foods, beverage, two-wheelers, holiday packages etc. are of great appeal to them.

In urban parts, the middle class woman is an active partner in the family. She is no longer confined to the four walls of the kitchen. She has acquired a place in society by virtue of her education and employment. She is a major factor in all purchase decisions of the family. She is practically the sole decision maker. Her role is main in purchasing-decisions. She is the cashier and budgeter. For several products, she is the 'gate-keeper'. New items cannot an entry into the house without her consent and clearance. Purchases meant for children too are mostly decided by her. In buying household appliances, she is often the sole decision-maker.

Characteristics of Women Consumer

The characteristics of women consumer are as given below

Cautious buyer:

The women are generally a cautious buyer. She is willing to try new things. She is not opposed to change. But she does not adopt any product instantly. She may do a sample purchase: she enquires with somebody who has known the product: she may listen to advertisements of the product: she decides to purchase only if she is fully satisfied.

The women are quality conscious as well as cost conscious buyer. She has often cross-checks the price details with other stores. She bargains, she compares one brand with another on price and quality. She has a tight family budget to follow and within this budget, she develops her own preferences whether it is baby; food, cooking medium, tea or coffee, cosmetics or readymade garments etc. She finds out what product or brand her neighbour or friend is using. She always gets direct information from an existing 'user' about the product.

Time-saving devices:

Time saving appliances hold out great charm to her. She prefers for gadgets like electric grinders, washing machine, dish-washers, pressure-cookers, microwave ovens, vacuum cleaner etc. As they reduce her workload and save her time to a great extent.

The women possess a good awareness of the changes taking place in her environment. Her education level and the growth in media have contributed to this development. TV and magazine etc., carry a lot of information targeted at her. They carry information on social, personal and family issues and messages on a variety of products and services. Since manufacturers need her patronage, they communicate with her through every possible media.

Sense of beauty:

Generally woman has fashion loving, but seldom fashion crazy. Soap or shampoo, face cream or moisturizer, perfumes or hair oil, in selecting her brand, she is greatly influenced by the massages that appeal to her sense of grooming.

Methodology:

The following aspects are considered in this section: The study includes the primary collection of data. This is a descriptive study using primary data collected through stratified sampling method with an adequate sample size of 30 respondents of Kerala. The study draws information from two sources i.e. primary source and secondary source. Primary Data were collected through questionnaire. This study includes a sample of 30 respondents comprising personal variables – age, sex, education, occupation, income.

Objective:

- (1)To analyse the buying behaviour of women for durable goods.
- (2)To analyse sources this attracts the purchasing attitude of women.

Hypothesis:-

Ho:-There is no significant difference in buying behavior of working women for durable goods remains the same irrespective of different groups of income.

Sample profile:-

Age

Age	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative percent
Less than 20 years	0		
20-30	20	66.66	66.66
30-40	5	16.66	83.32
More than 50	5	16.66	99.98
Total	30		

Table shows that 66.66 women are 20-30 years, 16.66 are 30-40 and 16.66 are 40-50

Income

Income	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative percent
Below-5000	0	0	0
5000-10000	6	20	20
15000-25000	12	40	60
25000-40000	6	20	80
Above 40000	6	20	100
Total	30	100	

Table shows that 5000-10000 women are 20%,15000-25000 are 40%,25000-40000 are 20% and above 40000 are 20%.

Occupation

Occupation	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative percent
Govt. employee	8	26.66	26.66
Private service	10	33.33	59.99
Business	6	20	79.99
Others	6	20	99.99
Total	30	100	

Table shows that govt. employees women are26.66%, private service women are 33.33%, women in business are 20%, women in other profession are 20%

Education

Education	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative percent
Graduate	0	0	0
Post graduate	12	40.00	40.00
Professionals	10	33.33	73.33
Others	8	26.66	99.99
Totals	30	100	

Table shows that post graduate women are 40%, professional women are 33.33%, women in other field are 26.66%

Table:-different aspects of product which attracts most

	Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative
Durability	6	20%	20
Price	4	13.33%	33.33
Discount	8	26.66%	59.99
Installment	6	20%	79.99
Guaranty/Warranty	6	20%	99.99
Total	30		

Table:-Brands of durable goods gets best with your life style.

Brands	Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative percentage
Samsung	8	26.66%	26.66%
L.G.	6	20%	46.66%
Godrej	4	13.33%	59.99%
Whirlpool	6	20%	79.99%
Videocon	6	20%	99.99%
Total	30		

Hypothesis testing:-

Ho There is no relationship between Income and the frequency of different aspects of product which attracts most.

Income	Durability	Price	Discount	Installment	Guaranty/Waranty	Total
5000-10000	2	1	1	1	1	6
15000-25000	3	2	1	2	4	12
25000-40000	1	1	1	1	2	6
Above 40000	1	1	1	2	1	6
Total	7	5	4	6	8	30

O _i	E _i	O _i -e _i	(O _i -e _i) ²	(O _i -e _i) ² /e _i
2	1.4	0.6	0.36	0.2571
1	1	0	0	0
1	.8	0.2	0.4	0.5
1	1.2	-0.2	.04	.0333
1	1.6	-.6	.36	0.225
3	2.8	0.2	.04	.01428
2	2	0	0	0
1	1.6	-.6	.36	0.225
2	2.4	-.4	.16	.0666
4	3.2	0.8	.64	0.2
1	1.4	-.4	.16	.11428
1	1	0	0	0
1	0.8	0.2	.04	0.05
1	1.2	-.2	.04	.0333
2	1.6	0.4	.16	0.1
1	1.4	-.4	.16	.11428
1	1	0	0	0
1	.8	0.2	.04	.05
2	1.2	-.2	.04	.0333
1	1.6	-.6	.36	.225
				2.24144

Degree of freedom

$$=(c-1)*(r-1) = (5-1)*(4-1) = 4*3 = 12$$

Level of significance = .05

The tabulated value of chi square at 12 degrees of freedom on .05 level of significance is 21.026 which is greater than calculated value (2.24144). It means hypothesis Ho is accepted. So we can say that income and different aspects of product like Durability, Price, Discount, Installment, Warranty/Guaranty has no relationship

Hypothesis testing:-

Ho Income and choice of brand of durable goods are independent or unrelated

Income	Samsung	L.G.	Whirlpool	Videocon	Total
5000-10000	2	2	1	1	6
15000-25000	4	2	2	4	12
25000-40000	2	2	1	1	6
Above 40000	2	1	1	2	6
	10	7	5	8	30

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O _i	E _i	O _i -e _i	(O _i -e _i) ²	(O _i e _i) ² /e _i
2	2	0	0	0
2	1.4	0.6	0.36	0.25714
1	1	0	0	0
1	1.6	-.6	0.36	0.225
4	4	0	0	0
2	2.8	-.8	0.64	0.2285
2	2	0	0	0
4	3.2	0.8	0.64	0.2
2	2	0	0	0
2	1.4	0.6	0.36	0.2571
1	1	0	0	0
1	1.6	-.6	0.36	0.225
2	2	0	0	0
1	1.4	-0.4	0.16	0.11428
1	1	0	0	0
2	1.6	0.4	0.16	0.1
				1.60702

Degree of freedom

=(c-1)*(r-1)

=(4-1)(4-1)

=(3)*(3)=9

Level of significance=.05

The tabulated value of chi square at 9 degrees of freedom on .05 level of significance is 16.919 which is greater than calculated value (1.60702). It means hypothesis Ho is accepted. So we can say that income and brand of durable goods gels best with life style are independent or unrelated

Result:-

According to responses in majority of cases null hypothesis is accepted. It means Income has no influence in the different aspects of product which attracts consumer towards product. So we can say that income and different aspects of product like Durability, Price, Discount, Installment, and Warranty/Guaranty has no relationship. Different brands of product are independent with income. So we can say women's are not bound towards income totally they take their own decision for purchasing the product.

Conclusion:-

Women, particularly women workforce are vital part of buying behaviour. It has been found that working women are more involved with the purchasing activities in Kerala. They are more price conscious as compared to the non-working married women. It has also been found that working women are more Store loyal than non-working married women. In case working women is more quality conscious than non-working married women. But non-working unmarried women are quality conscious. This study also prevails that there is a significant difference in buying behaviour of working women depending on what type of organization they work. Woman's role as the family purchasing agent, however, seems to be changing, due primarily to the large increase in the number of working women in recent decades. Therefore, working women has developed as an important segment for the marketers. Therefore, marketers should consider them with utmost importance.

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